

Perception of IT Professionals Towards Digital Currency Adoption in Mumbai

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Abstract:

The adoption of digital currencies has increased in recent years, because of advancements in technology and growing financial digitization. This study focuses on understanding how IT professionals in Mumbai view digital currencies. It aims to find out how much they know about digital currencies and how willing they are to use them. The study tries to understand the rate of digital currency adoption among the youth especially IT professionals as they are more prone to innovations and digital tools. The study also identifies what encourages or discourages IT professionals from using digital currencies. The study shows that IT professionals do have a positive attitude towards adopting digital currencies.

Keywords: Digital currency, IT professional, Mumbai, Adoption.

Introduction:

Digital currency:

Digital currency is a kind of currency that exists in only digital form or electronic form. Unlike traditional cash, modern technology uses blockchain method to keep transactions safe and transparent digital currency. They are often used in online transactions and they can be transferred electronically from one party to another. Digital currencies continue to gain acceptance and are being adopted by businesses and consumers worldwide. Digital currencies are typically classified into two types: Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC) and cryptocurrency.

Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC):

It's a digital currency which is created and controlled by a country's central bank such as the Reserve Bank of India or Federal Reserve. It's similar to ordinary cash but exists in only digital form. By using it we can do any transactions, just like cash or a credit card. CBDCs are safe, backed by the government, and make transactions faster

and smoother. Unlike cryptocurrencies like Bitcoin, CBDCs are not risky or unstable because they are regulated by the central bank.

Cryptocurrency:

It is digital money that is only in online form it is not controlled by banks and the government but it depends on technology like blockchain to keep it safe. Popular cryptocurrency is Bitcoin and Ethereum. People can use it to purchase things, send money and do any other transactions. To use it needs a digital wallet. Cryptocurrency wallets enable users to store, manage, and transfer their cryptocurrency holdings with different levels of security and convenience.

Review of Literature:

Aditya Kulkarni (2022) focused on how people reacted to the Digital Rupee in India after being introduced by the government in February 2022. study gives importance to how the digital rupee works, its characteristics, advantages and

challenges. The findings of the study helped to improve public opinion about the rupee before its launch.

Andrews, Rency, Neetha (2022): found out how much people know about digital currency. This study is based on a descriptive approach and it collected a sample of 60 people. They found that most of the population was aware of digital currency. In which bitcoin is well-known.

Brigid A. Appiah Otoo & Hamid Nemati (2017): studied the impact of using digital currency on people day to day lives especially in backwards areas. The study uses the European Central Bank's definition of digital currency, which describes it as a digital form of value that can replace money.

Ganesh S. Adgaonkar (2022): found that digital currency helps to boost the digital economy. Digital currency will also lead to a more effective and cheaper currency management system. The study is primarily based on secondary data collected from various journals, newspapers, articles and websites.

Guo, Xiaochun (2022): used various research methods to answer its main question. Data was gathered through interviews conducted over time. As a quantitative study, it applied bibliometric methods and network analysis. The research was organized into five chapters and was largely based on theoretical approaches.

Manpreet Kaur(2019): examined the global trends in digital currencies across specific countries and analysed the implications of digital currencies for India using a SWOT analysis. The Study is based on secondary data.

Md. Asraful Haque*and Mohd Shoaib (2023) studied how the e-rupee works and the differences between digital currency and cryptocurrency. It also studies about what are the main challenges faced by the e-rupee in India. They found that the use of digital currency it improving the security and reliability of the overall payment system.

Peter D. DeVries (2016): mentioned that cryptocurrency has the power to change the digital trade marketplace by creating a free-flowing trading system free of cost. This paper is based on primary data, data is collected from various published papers, articles and websites. The paper also studied the strengths and weaknesses of cryptocurrencies.

Shruti Sharma (2021) studied the impact of cryptocurrency on the investors and Indian economy. The main motive of the study is to understand the current situation of the digital currency. This research is based on a SWOT analysis. She found that the use of digital currency will help to improve the financial condition of the country.

T. Syahrul Reza (2018): explored professional solutions and explained how present cryptocurrency works all over the world, in which Bitcoin is a well-known currency. His studies aimed to find out how safe and reliable cryptography is. Also aim of the study is to explain how cryptocurrency works and its benefits until it is outdated.

Worakamol Wisetsri (2022): studied major development in academic research about the present state of cryptocurrency. It provides a quick summary of Bitcoin, including market capitalization data, Asian trends, India's participation, exchanges, international rules, environmental impact, and security.is also studied how the government and other institutes face this issue as well as the current legal framework of cryptocurrency in various countries.

Statement of The Problem:

Mumbai, India's financial hub is home to a diverse population and a thriving IT sector. With the rapid evolution of financial technology and the rise of digital currencies, a key question emerges—will IT professionals embrace these innovations, considering their benefits, security,

and efficiency? This study aims to assess the awareness, attitude, and perception of IT professionals toward adopting digital currencies. As metropolitan cities witness a surge in IT professionals and digital currencies gain global traction, understanding their acceptance becomes crucial. The insights from this research will be valuable for policymakers, businesses, and fintech innovators in shaping strategies for digital currency adoption and integration.

Objectives of The Study:

1. To assess the awareness and understanding of digital currencies among the IT professionals in Mumbai.
2. To analyse the attitude and willingness of IT professionals towards adopting digital currencies.

Hypotheses of The Study:

Hypothesis 01:

H0: IT professionals do not have significant awareness and understanding of digital currencies.

Ha: IT professionals have significant awareness and understanding of digital currencies.

Hypothesis 02:

H0: IT professionals do not have a positive attitude and willingness towards adopting digital currencies.

Ha: IT professionals have a positive attitude and a willingness towards adopting digital currencies.

Methodology of The Study:

Primary Data: This is a descriptive study based on the primary data collected by convenience sampling methods on 100 samples selected from the working individuals in IT industries in Mumbai. Data is collected through structured interviews consisting of close-ended and Linkert questions suited to the nature of the study.

Purposive sampling is used for this study focusing only on IT professionals.

Secondary data: To supplement this empirical study, secondary data is collected from the published papers, theses, articles and reports from various sources.

Significance of the Study:

The findings of the study help various businesses, and institutions to make policies and strategies that encourage the use of digital currency worldwide.

Analysis of the Data:

Based on the statistical analysis of IT professionals in Mumbai, the study reveals key insights into their awareness, attitude, and demographic differences regarding digital currency adoption.

1. Awareness & Attitude by Age Group

Age Group	Awareness Score	Attitude Score
21 to 30	3.40	3.92
31 to 40	3.09	3.67
41 to 50	2.00	2.00
51 and above	4.00	4.33

Observations: It is observed that younger respondents between the age group 21- 30 have moderate awareness but positive attitudes towards adopting digital currency. The residents between the ages of 31-40 have slightly lower awareness but keep a positive attitude. And the respondents from the age group 41 -50 have the lowest awareness and show willingness. And the respondents above 51 and above show the highest awareness and willingness. The analysis is done on the awareness and attitude scores of the respondents towards adopting digital currency.

2. Awareness & Attitude by Gender

Gender	Awareness Score	Attitude Score
Female	3.62	4.00
Male	3.00	3.71

Observation: Females have higher awareness (3.62) and a stronger positive attitude (4.00) towards digital currency than males.

3. Awareness & Attitude by Occupation

IT Sector	Awareness Score	Attitude Score
Cybersecurity	3.50	3.53
Data Analysis & BI	3.71	4.20
ERP & CRM Systems	1.00	4.57
IT Support/Operations	3.57	3.91
Networking & Telecom	3.17	4.00
Other	3.00	3.86
Software Development	3.11	3.53

Observations: Data Analysts & Business Intelligence professionals have the highest awareness (3.71) and strong willingness (4.20). ERP & CRM professionals have very low awareness (1.00) but high willingness (4.57). Software developers & cybersecurity professionals show moderate awareness (3.11-3.50) but lower willingness (3.53).

Test Anova and T-Test:

1. Awareness & Attitude by Age (ANOVA)

Metric	F-Statistic	P-Value	Significance (p < 0.05)
Awareness by Age	0.711	0.551	No Significant Difference
Attitude by Age	2.329	0.081	No Significant Difference

Interpretation: Awareness and attitude do not significantly differ across age groups. Although

younger and older individuals show differences in means, these differences are **not statistically significant**.

2. Awareness & Attitude by Occupation (ANOVA)

Metric	F-Statistic	P-Value	Significance (p < 0.05)
Awareness by Occupation	1.007	0.436	No Significant Difference
Attitude by Occupation	2.257	0.046	Significant Difference

Interpretation: Awareness does not significantly vary across occupations. Attitude towards adopting digital currency significantly differs by occupation (p = 0.046). This means some occupations are significantly more willing to adopt digital currency than others.

3. Awareness & Attitude by Gender (T-Test)

Metric	T-Statistic	P-Value	Significance (p < 0.05)
Awareness (Male vs Female)	-1.797	0.080	No Significant Difference
Attitude (Male vs Female)	-1.485	0.143	No Significant Difference

Interpretations: There is no significant difference in awareness or attitude between males and females. Although females show higher mean awareness and willingness, the differences are not statistically significant.

Hypothesis Testing:

Hypothesis 1: Awareness and Understanding of Digital Currencies

Null Hypothesis (H₀): IT professionals do not have significant awareness and understanding of digital currencies in Mumbai.

Alternative Hypothesis (H₁): IT professionals have significant awareness and understanding of digital currencies.

Statistical Results:**Mean Awareness Score: 3.30**

(on a scale of 1 to 5)

T-Statistic: 1.70**P-Value: 0.0964****Decision:** Since $p\text{-value} > 0.05$, we fail to reject the null hypothesis.

There is no statistically significant evidence that individuals have a strong awareness and understanding of digital currencies. Their awareness level is moderate but not significantly high.

Hypothesis 2: Attitude and Willingness to Adopt Digital Currencies**Null Hypothesis (H₀₂):** IT professionals do not have a positive attitude and willingness towards adopting digital currencies.**Alternative Hypothesis (H₁₂):** IT professionals have a positive attitude and willingness towards adopting digital currencies.**Statistical Results:****Mean Attitude Score: 3.87** (on a scale of 1 to 5)**T-Statistic: 9.25****P-Value: 2.08×10^{-14}** (very small)**Decision:** Since $p\text{-value} < 0.05$, we reject the null hypothesis.

There is strong statistical evidence that individuals have a positive attitude and willingness towards adopting digital currencies.

Summary of Findings:

Hypothesis	Mean Score	T-Statistic	P-Value	Decision
H ₀₁ : Awareness	3.30	1.70	0.0964	Fail to Reject (Not Significant)
H ₀₂ : Attitude	3.87	9.25	2.08×10^{-14}	Reject (Significant)

Results: Awareness is moderate but not significantly high. Attitude & willingness to adopt digital currency is significantly positive.

Major Findings:

While IT professionals have some knowledge about digital currencies, their awareness is not significantly high, indicating a need for more education and exposure.

IT professionals are generally open to adopting digital currencies, but their level of willingness varies by job role, with some sectors being more receptive than others.

Adoption patterns are job-role dependent, indicating that industries like data analytics and ERP might be early adopters of digital currency.

Limitation of the Study:

- This study is only conducted on IT professionals in Mumbai.
- This study cannot be generalized to all individuals in Mumbai.

Conclusion:

The study finds that IT professionals in Mumbai have a moderate awareness but a significantly positive attitude towards adopting digital currencies. Awareness needs improvement, suggesting that educational efforts and exposure to digital currency concepts could be beneficial. Willingness to adopt is strong, particularly among professionals in Data Analytics & ERP sectors. Occupation plays a crucial role in adoption willingness, whereas age and gender do not significantly impact perception.

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